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INTERPRETATION OF THE PHENOMENON OF PUBLICISTIC DISCOURSE IN LINGUISTICS

ABSTRACT: This article focuses on the term discourse in mass communication, which is one of the vital issues in pragmatic and cognitive linguistics, a field that is emerging as a new trend in modern linguistics. The term “discourse” has been coined in the field of linguistics. Despite its initial understanding as a connected and accepted consequence in speech or in text, it is defined in linguistics by its interpretation as a complicated communicative event in modern linguistics.

KEY WORDS: discourse, media style, publicistic discourse, cognitive linguistics, speech, text, journalistic discourse, political discourse

The study's conceptual foundation is the view of discourse as a phenomenon generated by cognitive, linguistic, ideological, social, and cultural aspects including politics, psychology, and linguistics. The publicistic discourse as a phenomenon created by a specific situation and specific phenomena associated with global events and existing in time and space. It takes into account various strategies underpinning the extralinguistic situation, as well as the characteristics of

communication participants, including language personality. That is why we consider interpreting the term “discourse” initially.

For the first time, “discourse” was introduced into the scientific theory of text linguistics by the American scientist Z. Harris in 1952 as a linguistic term in the phrase “discourse analysis”. Thus, the concept of “discourse”, borrowed from structural linguistics, receives an increasingly broad scientific interpretation

and terminological ambiguity at the end of the twentieth century [1, p.1].

To the definition of online etymology dictionary the phenomenon “discourse” was defined as ides in words: “late 14c., “process of understanding, reasoning thought,” from French discours, from Latin discursus “a running about,” in Late Latin “conversation,” in Medieval Latin “reasoning,” noun use of past participle of discurre “to run about, run to and fro, hasten,” in Late Latin “to go over a subject, speak at length of, discourse of,” from dis- “apart” + currere “to run”. Meaning “a running over a subject in speech, communication of thought in words” is from 1550s; sense of “discussion or treatment of a subject in formal speech or writing,” is from 1580s [2, online dictionary].

Furthermore, the term “discourse” stands for “communication in speech or writing” in Cambridge dictionary [3, online dictionary].

The Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Modern English defines discourse as “a unit of written or spoken language used to produce meaning and is also stated as long discussions in the speech or text [4, online dictionary].

Based on the linguistic theory, current research is conducted with the help of fundamental works of both domestic and foreign scientists that are complex and interdisciplinary in nature. Namely,

cognitive linguist Sh.Safarov conducted an important analysis and certain definitions to the phenomenon “discourse” [5, pp. 67-95]. Sh. Safarov claimed accurately H. Haberland’s viewpoints as “discourse is an event that is happening at certain time and place, but it is in process. Text can be used for several times and can be transferred from one to another place. However, discourse is happening at present, it creates itself every time. Text is the product aspect of language [5, p.245] then he identified the term clearly “discourse must be defined wider than text and at the same time, it is the result of linguistic process” [5, p.249]. We do agree to Sh. Safarov’s hypothesis, discourse is the communication process in spoken language and language beyond the sentence under the discourse.

To the viewpoints of Nikitina, Juliya Lebedinskaya, Oksana Plakhova, Olga, the term of discourse was outlined in detail: “as a synthesis of different authors’ interpretations, the discursive terminology is found in the work “Theory and practice of discourse” by P. Serio. “Discourse” is shown as:

- 1) an equivalent to the concept of “speech” (F. Saussure),
- 2) a unit size superior to that of a phrase,
- 3) the impact of the statements on its recipients taking into account the situation of the utterance,
- 4) a conversation as the main type of speech,

- 5) a speech from the position of the speaker as opposed to a narrative, which does not account for such a position (for E. Benveniste),
- 6) the usage of language units, their speech actualization,
- 7) socially or ideologically restricted type of expressions, for example, feminist discourse,
- 8) a theoretical construct designed to research the conditions of production of the text [6, p.2].

In most modern works of domestic and foreign scientists (Sh. Safarov, Arutyunova, van Dyke, Karasik, Kibrik, Makarov, etc.), a tradition has developed in which the word discourse is understood as an integral speech work in the diversity of its cognitive and communicative functions.

The purpose of the media (Internet broadcasts, newspapers, magazines, radio, and television) is to inform readers, viewers, and audiences on what is going on in the globe. It is only natural that they're the fastest-changing and most-evolving field, both in terms of content (including languages) and form (representing changes in mass-media discourse related to the social environment and politics). As a result, newspaper and magazine articles, as well as radio and television scripts, have tremendous value for analyzing language change and developing skills and capacities in all sorts of speech activity, including reading, listening, writing, and speaking.

In publicistic discourse, the function of influence (agitation and propaganda) of language is realized, with which the informative function (the message of the new) is often combined. The mass media materials touch upon issues of a very wide range of topics:

topical issues of modernity of interest to society (political, economic, moral, philosophical),

issues of culture, education, everyday life.

Publicistic discourse finds application in socio-political literature, periodicals (newspapers, magazines), oratory, etc.

To our hypothesis, one of the sorts of media speech is publicistic discourse and it has become vital in modern linguistics. The main features of the publicistic discourse include:

Figure 1. The main characteristics of publicistic discourse.

We can take the following conclusions after studying the theoretical material:

1) In modern linguistics, the term "discourse" is used ambiguously to represent current speech activity in which - either in the domain and to designate a coherent text in combination with extralinguistic - pragmatic, sociocultural, psychological, and other aspects.

2) Media discourse is a complex communication phenomenon aimed at creating public opinion, which includes text as a verbalized consequence of speech, context - situational and, as well as specialized language tools and communicative techniques that fit the discourse's goals and objectives.

3) One of the sorts of media speech is publicistic discourse. The journalistic text, which has a political and ideological method of text creation, is the core unit of this discourse.

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